

The Influence of Psychological Capital on Work Engagement at PT Pelindo I (persero)

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Abstract— This study aims to analyze the influence of psychological capital on work engagement at PT Pelindo I (persero). Respondents of this study are permanent employees at the head office of PT Pelindo I (persero). Data were analyzed statistically by using multiple regression. The result showed that psychological capital (PsyCap) were significant factors in elevating work engagement. The implication of this research that management must be able to focus on developing psychological capital by giving many relevant programs to increase work engagement.

Keywords— Psychological capital, work engagement, port company, permanent employee.

I. INTRODUCTION

PT Pelabuhan Indonesia I (persero) is a company in the field of port services. This State-Owned Enterprise or abbreviated as BUMN was built for establishing a profit and providing services to the general public. The company dominated by Indonesian government and established in 1960 with the function as a government solution in managing public ports in Indonesia. The working area of the company PT Pelabuhan Indonesia I (Persero) includes North Sumatra (North Sumatra), Riau, Riau Islands and the Province of Nanggroe Aceh Darussalam (NAD). The head office of PT Pelindo I is located in Medan North Sumatra. In 2018, PT Pelindo I (Persero) has a total of 1433 permanent employees (www.pelindo1.co.id).

PT Pelindo I (Persero) is one of the largest port services in Indonesia. In 2014, the transformation of human resources (HR) on PT Pelindo I (persero) began to improve professional knowledge and competence, as well as transformation in all other managerial aspects. Continuous transformation is carried out to encourage better management of the company, so it can ensure the business growth and performance on PT Pelindo I (persero) (Pelindo I Annual Report, 2015).

After the transformation, the work engagement of employees in the company increased. Schaufelli, Salanova, Roma, and Baker (2002) define work engagement as conditions or positive self-conditions in relation to their work characterized by the dimensions of vigor, dedication and absorption. Work engagement is also defined by the positive attitude that exists in employees with regard to all values and goals of the organization (Robinson, Perryman & Hayday, 2004). According to Wellins and Concelman (2005) work attachment is a strength of self that can motivate individuals to achieve performance at high level.

According to Bakker and Demerouti (2008) thing that capable of causing high and low work engagement is personal resource factors. Personal resource factors consist of self-

efficacy, optimism, and hope. Luthans and Youssef (2007) add resilience as part of a personal resource factor called psychological capital. Psychological capital is a positive psychological condition in a person with characteristics such as self-confidence in an effort to work on challenging responsibilities (self-efficacy); have a sense of optimism about success now and in the future (optimism); diligently trying to achieve goals and have hope (hope); have self-resistance to solve problems and always have the desire to achieve success (resilience).

Bakker and Demerouti (2008) state that employees who are engaged will have psychological capital that is different from other employees. In addition, any changes in the organization require individuals who have strong personal resources, such as Fachruddin and Mangundjaya (2012) research which states that psychological capital is part of the positive aspects of individuals that also affect readiness in transformation. The existence of psychological capital makes individuals motivated to develop in any situation. The results of research conducted by Hedissa (2012) state that psychological capital if the higher the employee is, the better the performance of the employee in completing the assignment.

The explanation above shows that work engagement can influenced by psychological capital. Therefore, the researchers are interested in conducting a research on the influence of psychological capital on work engagement at PT Pelindo I (persero).

II. OBJECTIVES & METHODS

The main objective of this study was to examine the influence of psychological capital on work engagement at PT Pelindo I (persero). Sampling technique was incidental sampling with 135 employees. Data were collected using work engagement scale and psychological capital scale.

Work engagement scale is based on Schaufelli, Salanova, Roma and Baker theory (2002): vigor, dedication, absorption. The reliability test result is .895. Psychological capital scale is based on Luthans and Youssef theory (2007): hope, optimism, self efficacy and resilience. The reliability test results is .878.

Both scale used Likert model with five answer choices that were very inappropriate, inappropriate, neutral, appropriate and very appropriate. The score for every aitem moved from 1 to 5, with a score point 1 for very inappropriate choices up to a score point 5 for very appropriate.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The result of this study indicate that there is an influence of psychological capital on work engagement. This research is also in line with the research of Hodges (2010) who found that psychological capital supports the emergence of work engagement, such as spirit, energy and enthusiasm and provide more effort in carrying out work to achieve goals. Othman and Nasurdin's research (2012) shows that two predictors of research variables namely hope and resiliency are dimensions in psychological capital that have a relationship with work engagement. Sihag and Sarikwal (2014) state that there is a positive relationship between psychological capital and work engagement. Herbert (2011) in his study revealed that the dimensions of optimism and self-efficacy of psychological capital emerged as two of the strongest predictors affecting employee attachment. In a study conducted by Xanthopoulou, Bakker, Demerouti and Schaufeli (2007) about three personal resources (efficacy, hope and optimism) show the results that employees who are engaged, believe that they will achieve the best results in their lives and can participate in their roles in organization.

Psychological capital has a positive effect on employee engagement due to the efficacy dimension, when individuals want to complete tasks and work accomplishments, they automatically increase vigor because they require a lot of energy. Therefore the dimension of efficacy on psychological capital is related to the dimension of vigor on work engagement (Sweetman & Luthans, 2010). In addition, optimistic individuals will reduce cynicism towards job demands and automatically increase their dedication to work (Karasek in Kain & Jex, 2010). When optimism is formed, individuals try to achieve positive results in their work, so this will lead them to a higher sense of engagement to their profession or work (Kahn, 1990). In short, optimism is directly related to the dimension of dedication to work engagement (Sweetman & Luthans, 2010).

Employees who are engaged have self-efficacy, optimism and high hope. Hope is a way to achieve goals related to the dimensions of vigor in work engagement. With hope, individuals will give the best effort from themselves, so that the effort will automatically make them feel always engaged to their work (Sweetman & Luthans, 2010). Resilience is related to the capacity to adapt positively to any changes that occur to the organization (Luthans & Youssef, 2007). With regard to work demands, this dimension is associated with absorption. Employees mobilize resilient behavior through motivation in their work attachments, so that it deals with vigor and absorption (Sweetman & Luthans, 2010). Therefore,

when individuals have psychological capital, this will encourage the creation of individual work engagement (Xanthopoulou, Bakker, Demerouti & Schaufeli, 2007).

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, it was concluded that psychological capital can increase work engagement. The implication of this research that management must be able to focus on developing psychological capital by giving many relevant programs to increase work engagement.

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